

The role of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals to achieve patient safety goals: Literature review

Lailatul Maghfiroh *

Department of Health Policy and Administration, Faculty of Public Health, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 20(02), 097–102

Publication history: Received on 16 September 2023; revised on 28 October 2023; accepted on 30 October 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.2.2181>

Abstract

Patient safety is an action taken to minimize hazards during a patient's healthcare experience, particularly in hospitals. Patient safety can be described as a system in which hospitals implement improved nursing care processes. Objectives: To understand and analyze the role of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals to achieve the standards of patient safety goals. Methods: The article search was conducted through the PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar databases using the keywords "patient safety" AND "nurse's role" OR "nurse" AND "hospital" AND "patient safety goals". The search yielded a total of 119 articles, but only 10 articles met the inclusion criteria. Result: A study conducted in 7 hospitals in Indonesia and other countries revealed several roles of nurses in implementing patient safety. The most commonly found role was nurses providing nursing care using the nursing process. Nurses also delivered optimal nursing care and services while ensuring equitable distribution of care. Additionally, nurses supported and advocated for the well-being of patients. Conclusion: The roles of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals can be grouped into three categories: care roles, education roles, advocacy roles, and collaboration roles.

Keywords: The role of nurses; Patient safety; Hospitals; Patient safety goals.

1. Introduction

Patient safety is also interpreted as a system in which hospitals make patient care safer [1]. Safety has become a global issue, including safety in hospitals. Patient safety is one of the main priorities implemented in health services, especially in hospitals. Patient safety is related to the quality and image of the health service itself [2]. Meanwhile, it is also defined as efforts made to prevent events that have bad effects on patients so that they can cause complications by implementing quality practices and producing optimal health services [3].

The goal of patient safety is to prevent incidents that result in injury due to errors resulting from carrying out wrong actions. In accordance with the standards currently used, namely The Six Goal International Patient Safety from JCI which consists of (1) Identify patients correctly, (2) Increase effective communications (improve effective communications), (3) Increase safety. in high-risk medications (improve the safety of high alert medications), (4) Ensure the correct location, procedure and patient during surgical operations (ensure correct site, correct procedure, correct patient surgery), (5) Reduce the risk of nosocomial infections (reduce the risk of health care associated infections), (6) Reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls) [4].

According to WHO, from reporting results in developed countries, adverse events or adverse events in inpatients are 3%. In New Zealand, adverse events are reported to be around 12.9% of the number of inpatients, while in England, adverse events (KTD) are around 10.8% [5]. Patient safety incidents in Indonesia in 2016 recorded by KKP-RS based on province showed that DKI Jakarta Province had the highest number, namely 37.9% greater than the other eight

* Corresponding author: Lailatul Maghfiroh

provinces. Therefore nurses in hospitals have such an important role in improving patient safety so that nurses really need to have good knowledge about their role when providing services to patients in hospitals [6].

Seeing the high number of patient safety incidents that occur in health services, researchers are increasingly interested in knowing the role of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals in order to achieve standard patient safety goals. By knowing what role nurses play in implementing patient safety in hospitals, researchers hope this will help reduce the number of patient safety incidents, reduce errors in taking action and provide an idea to stakeholders in planning and establishing patient safety policies according to standards.

2. Material and methods

The method that researchers used in writing this article was a literature review. Data collection in this article was carried out through three data base sources, namely PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. The keywords used in the article search were: "patient safety" AND "nurse's role" OR "nurse" AND "hospital" AND "patient safety goals". The search for articles in the database was limited to articles published by year within the last 5 years (2019 to 2023). Articles used by researchers are in the form of original articles, full text and open access. There were 10 articles that were considered appropriate and met the inclusion criteria.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the search results, there are a total of studies conducted in 7 hospitals located in Indonesia and outside countries including: Medan (n = 2), Gorontalo (n = 1), Manado (n = 1), Jakarta (n = 2), Purwodadi (n = 1), Philippines (n = 1), California (n = 1), United States (n = 1). There are two articles published in 2023, four articles published in 2021, two articles published in 2020, two articles published in 2019. Of the 10 articles selected, 5 articles used a quantitative research method with a cross-sectional design (n = 4) and descriptive cross-sectional (n = 1). While 5 articles used qualitative research methods with a case study design (n = 1), descriptive analysis (n = 2) and 2 articles used a mixture of quantitative and qualitative methods. Based on a search of the articles collected and the author's analysis it was found that:

Tabel 1 List of articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Halawa <i>et al</i> [7]	Nurses' Perceptions of Their Role in Improving Patient Safety	Penelitian ini adalah penelitian kualitatif dengan metode <i>Focus Group Discussion</i> (FGD)	Nurses provide education to patients and families. Protect patients from events such as errors in drug administration. Work closely with the head of the room to always remind subordinates to always implement patient safety goals.
2.	Talib <i>et al</i> [4]	The Role of Nurses in Patient Safety at the Otanaha General Hospital, Gorontalo	This research is a descriptive survey research. This research was conducted at Otanaha Hospital, in June-July 2022.	Nurses as care givers. Nurses remind each other, direct, delegate between nurses and nurses. Collaborate with other healthcare teams in interprofessional interventions.
3.	Rottie [2]	The Relationship between the Nurse's Role in Handover and the Implementation of Patient Safety at RSI Sitti Maryam Manado	The research design used in this study is a "Cross sectional study"	Nurse communication in carrying out nursing care to patients. Provide information about the current condition of the patient.
4.	Mulidan & Afina [8]	The Role of Nurses Implementing Interprofessional Collaboration (IPC) in Nursing Care of Covid-19 Patients	The method used is a qualitative method with a descriptive phenomenological approach. Data	The nurse accompanies the visiting doctor, during the visit the nurse provides input and suggestions according to science. Nurses collaborate with

			collection was carried out by FGD (Focus Group Discussion) and in-depth interviews.	multiprofessions when providing nursing care.
5.	Chotimah [9]	The Role of Nurses in Preventing the Risk of Patient Falls in Hospital Inpatient Rooms	The research is descriptive research. This study used a cross sectional approach	Nurses make efforts to prevent the risk of falls. Nurses provide nursing care.
6.	Wiratmo <i>et al</i> [10]	The Relationship Between Knowledge and Attitudes of Nurses Regarding Patient Safety Against the Implementation of the Nursing Early Warning Scoring System (NEWSS)	The research design is correlative quantitative cross sectional.	The nurse applies NEWSS to a patient in the surgery recovery room.
7.	Wiadayati <i>et al</i> [11]	The Role of Nurses in Implementing Patient Safety and Protecting Patient Rights at Rahayu Yakkum Purwodadi Hospital	The method used in this research is sociological juridical research. The specification of the research in this thesis is analytic descriptive.	Nurses wash their hands before and after examining patients, and after being exposed to fluids from patients. The nurse takes care of the safety of the medicine. Nurses carry out health education to patients and families. Nurses provide protection of patient rights which shows that there are arrangements related to patient safety.
8.	Al-Yateem <i>et al</i> [12]	Nurse-identified patient care and health services research priorities in the United Arab Emirates: a Delphi study	A two-phase Delphi design was implemented with 1032 nurses participating in phase one of the study and 1339 in phase two.	Nurses contribute to improving the health of individuals, families, communities and populations. Nurses ensure the well-being of patients, and create a caring environment
9.	Feliciano <i>et al</i> [13]	Philippine professional core competencies' impact on nurses' key performance indicators (KPIs) for patient safety outcomes	This study uses a descriptive-correlation design	Nurses provide acceptable, safe and quality patient care. Nurses are responsible for maintaining a safe hospital work environment on a regular basis to create a positive impact on patient safety. The nurse directly observes safety issues in the clinical area.
10.	Carthon <i>et al</i> [14]	<i>Association of Nurse Engagemnt and Nurse Staffing on Patient Safety</i>	Secondary analysis of the related cross-sectional data was conducted using survey data	Higher involvement of nurses in the implementation of patient safety. Nurse participation in decision making in the health care system.

Table 2 Grouping the role of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals to achieve patient safety goals

Parenting Role	Educational Role	Advocacy Role	Collaborative Roles
Nurses as care givers use the nursing process. Providing maximum nursing care and services. Providing equitable services in a fair manner. Nurses support and improve the welfare of patients.	Nurses assist patients in increasing the level of health knowledge, symptoms of disease and even the actions given. Nurses can also provide health educators to high-risk family groups, health cadres, and so on	Nurses play a role in maintaining and protecting patients' rights which include the right to the best possible service, the right to information about their illness and the right to privacy. Nurses help patients and their families in interpreting various information from service providers or other information, especially in taking consent for nursing actions given to patients.	Nurse participation in decision making with other health teams in the health care system. Nurses collaborate with multiprofessions when providing nursing care.

3.1. Parenting Role

The role of care is the provision of nursing services by nurses who are carried out using nursing methods. In this case, nurses can pay attention to basic human needs to provide good nursing care services. Nurses in implementing patient safety must be able to serve patients well, be caring, and respect patients. Based on the results of research by [4] it shows that the role of nurses as care givers is categorized as good at 100%. Of all the respondents, a total of 34 respondents, overall the nurse carried out her role as a care giver/nursing care giver.

In line with research conducted by [9] states that one form of nursing care is regarding nurse compliance in preventing the risk of patient falls. Efforts to prevent the risk of falls are one of the main keys to realizing patient safety, so it has become an important part of nursing services. Efforts to prevent the risk of falls are said to be actions to prevent patients from danger or falls while the patient is undergoing treatment and treatment.

3.2. Educational Role

The educational role is a role carried out by nurses to increase knowledge about health, symptoms of disease or even actions given, so that changes in patient behavior can be assessed after health education. In research, [7] stated that one of the roles of nurses in implementing patient safety is providing education to patients and families regarding the patient's health. The statement has similarities with Jang & Lee's research [7] that nurses carry out their role to encourage patients and families to achieve health, educate patients and families about things that must be done or things that should not be done during undergoing treatment or treatment.

Nurses provide education and skills development for family caregivers, and emphasize increasing knowledge and education regarding the symptoms of the disease they are suffering from. To enable skill development, they focus on symptom management and less on medication organization and administration. The role of nurses in providing education and support regarding treatment and symptom management to patients and their family caregivers requires optimal communication to ensure treatment safety in order to implement patient safety according to Patient Safety Goals standards [15]

3.3. Advocacy Role

The advocacy role is a role carried out by nurses to protect and defend patients. In research, [7] explained that the advocacy role carried out by nurses is one of them by protecting patients from incidents of errors in administering medication. Apart from that, the role of the nurse is to protect the patient from events that harm the patient both physically and materially. Therefore, when carrying out an action it must be carried out in accordance with established standard operational procedures.

According to data obtained in a study by [11], data on patient safety incidents obtained at Panti Rahayu Yakkum Purwodadi Hospital in 2015 totaled 48 cases of patient safety incidents while in 2016 these incidents continued to

increase to 67 cases. Through this data, it can be seen that nurses have not fully carried out their advocacy role to protect patients. If the nurse's role in implementing Patient Safety is not implemented properly, it will affect the protection of patient rights. Therefore, in providing health services performed by nurses, they must pay attention to protecting the rights of patients as a form of nurse's advocacy role.

3.4. Collaborative Role

The role of nurse collaboration is the role of cooperation between nurses and other health teams in the process of nursing services needed such as discussions or exchanging opinions in determining the next form of service. Each profession is required to have a professional attitude in a team that must understand and respect other professions so that the services provided can provide satisfaction for patients and other professions [8].

The same thing can also be seen from the results of Cecillia Heni Agustinawati's research [4], indicating that nurses understand their role as collaborators in the implementation of discharge planning in the care process, namely working together with other health teams. The nurse's role as an ongoing collaborator with the nursing process. Meanwhile, according to Nurjasmii [4], the role of nurses as collaborators is carried out because nurses work together through other health teams consisting of doctors, physiotherapists, nutritionists and others by trying to identify nursing services needed including discussions or exchanges opinions in determining the form of further services.

4. Conclusion

The results of the literature review show that the role of nurses in implementing patient safety in hospitals in order to achieve standardized patient safety goals can be grouped into 4 roles, namely the role of care, the role of education, the role of advocacy, and the role of collaboration. The role of care relates to the nurse as a care giver by using the nursing process while providing maximum nursing care and services. While the role of education is related to nurses helping patients in increasing the level of health knowledge, symptoms of disease and even the actions given. Then for the advocacy role, the nurse plays a role in defending and protecting patient rights which include the right to the best possible service, the right to information about their illness and the right to privacy. As for the collaborative role of nurses, they collaborate with multiprofessions when providing nursing care. Therefore, the role of nurses is needed in implementing patient safety in hospitals to achieve patient safety goals.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

Author acknowledge the reviewer's positive suggestions on this paper.

References

- [1] Rosiana I, Ekorini L. Implementation of Patient Safety Orientation SOP: Aisyiyah Study at Kudus Regional Hospital. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan*. 2023; 8(S1): 225-230.
- [2] Rottie JV. The Relationship between the Nurse's Role in Handover and the Implementation of Paise Safety at RSI Sitti Maryam Manado. *Jurnal Kesehatan*. 2021; 2(14): 1-5.
- [3] Menkes RI, Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2017. Concerning Hospital Patient Safety. Jakarta: Menkes, R.I., 2017.
- [4] Talib AS, Sabirin BS, Fadlin S. The Role of Nurses in Patient Safety at the Otanaha Gorontalo Regional General Hospital. *Journal of Educational Innovation and Public Health*. 2023; 1(2): 91-101.
- [5] Huriati. Quality of patient safety services in hospitals. *Forum Ekonomi*. 2022; 24(1): 186– 194.
- [6] Widayati CN, Sulistyarini. Legal Protection for Patients in the Implementation of Patient Safety by Nurses at Panti Rahayu Yakkum Hospital. *TSCD3Kep Journal*. 2021; 6(2): 33-46.
- [7] Halawa A, Setiawan, Bustani S. Nurses' Perceptions of their Role in Improving Patient Safety. *Journal of Telenursing*. 2021; 3(1): 73-84.
- [8] Mulidan, Afina MS. The Role of Nurses in Implementing Interprofessional Collaboration (IPC) in Nursing Care for Covid-19 Patients. *Jurnal Keperawatan*. 2023; 15(1): 321-330.

- [9] Chotimah C. The Role of Nurses in Preventing the Risk of Patient Falls in the Inpatient Room at Medistra Hospital, Jakarta, 2019. *Jurnal Kesehatan "Bhakti Husada"*. 2021; 7(1): 1-11.
- [10] Wiratmo PA, Ulfah NK, Linda P. The Relationship Between Knowledge and Attitudes of Nurses Regarding Patient Safety on the Implementation of the Nursing Early Warning Scoring System (NEWS). *Journals of Ners Community*. 2021; 12(2): 232-244.
- [11] Wiadayati CN, Endang WY, Hadi S. The Role of Nurses in Implementing Patient Safety and Protecting Patient Rights at Rahayu Yakkum Purwodadi Hospital. *Jurnal Hukum Kesehatan*. 2019; 5(2): 254-268.
- [12] Al-Yateem N, Muna AT, Maria B, Hanan AT. *Nurse-identified patient care and health services research priorities in the United Arab Emirates: a Delphi study*. *BMC Health Service Research*. 2019; 19(77): 2-8.
- [13] Feliciano AZ, Evelyn EF, Joan RDF, Anita BV. Philippine professional core competencies' impact on nurses' key performance indicators (KPIs) for patient safety outcomes. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*. 2020; 7(1): 1-5.
- [14] Carthon JMB, Lawrence D, Andrew D, Linda HA. Association of Nurse Engagement and Nurse Staffing on Patient Safety. *J Nurs Care Qual*. 2020; 34(1): 40-46.
- [15] Mardani A, Paulin G, Mojtaba V. The Role of the Nurse in the Management of Medicines During Transitional Care: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*. 2022; 13: 347-361.